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GEOELEC

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Proposal for creating National Committees on geothermal power in EU Member States

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Introduction

One objective of the GEOELEC project is to promote across the EU the creation of National Geothermal Committees.

This initiative is coming from France where such a Committee has already been established in July 2010: The Energy Ministry launched a 'Comité National de la géothermie' to propose actions and recommendations for a geothermal development in France.

It is composed by 35 members from 5 different sectors:

- State level
- Local authorities
- NGOs
- Employers
- Workers

Meetings are organised regularly (every 2 months) and the Secretariat is managed directly by the Ministry

The first Results of the *Comité National de la géothermie* in France can be presented through 3 key actions:

- Simplifying administrative procedure and quality
- Training professionals
- Disseminating information

Finally, the goal being to consolidate the French position as a leading geothermal country. the Key objectives are to :

- Multiply the geothermal production by 6
- Create 80 000 jobs in the geothermal sector

We contacted one member of this Committee in order to receive his feedback (C. Boissavy, President AFPG 'French geothermal association'). He highlighted the fact that it is a real opportunity for professionals of the geothermal sector to:

- Speak directly with the State Authorities
- Dialogue with the « Greens » and with representatives from the Civil Society
- Trade unions and consumer associations are the most motivated
- Need a high level person as President

The objective is to make a proposal to Energy Ministries and National Energy Agencies of several member States.

The goal is to see the creation of such a Committee in 4-5 countries during the next 30 months

Activities

A dedicated presentation has been made during the 7 Geoelec workshops organised between September 2011 and March 2012, and already many positive feed-backs have been received. For this purpose CRES held two meetings, the first one with the Ministry of environment, energy and climate change of Greece and the second with the PPC-Renewables company which owns 8 high enthalpy geothermal concessions in Greece, with promising results.

GEOELEC Proposal

Creation of National Geothermal Committees

Regional Workshop

Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia, Finland, Sweden,
Ukraine

Philippe DUMAS

European Geothermal Energy Council

Vilnius, 22/03/2012

Then, national authorities were contacted and invited to the promotional seminars which were new opportunities for promoting this idea.

Finally, GEOELEC partners sent in October-November 2013 a letter to all EU-28 Ministries of Energy (see annex I) asking them the creation of a National Geothermal Committee in their Country.

Feedback

Germany:

In the run-up to the elections and the formation of a new German government in 2013, the timing was not considered to be appropriate to place an initiative for the creation of a new German geothermal committee.

So the German GEOELEC project partners organized various activities of dissemination with policy and decision makers at the local, regional and national levels to promote geothermal electricity. Some events were linked with the leading German associations in the field of renewable energies in Germany, the GtV-BV, the WFG and the FVEE.

The "German Association of Geothermal Energy (GtV-BV)" represents the common

interests of the German geothermal community covering the whole range of geothermal energy technologies, from shallow to deep, from heating and cooling to electricity supply.

The “Economic Forum of Geothermal Energy” (WFG)” is an association of leading companies active in the field of geothermal energy production in Switzerland and Germany.

The forum provides a platform for professionals from all relevant sectors (finance, geology, engineering, ...) for knowledge and experience exchange. Additionally the WFG is a contact for politicians and private bodies interested in geothermal energy production.

The “Forschungsverbund Erneuerbare Energien (FVEE)” is the network of the leading German non-university research centres. In the framework of strategic partnerships the member-institutes define long-term research objectives and assignments by networking their activities and know-how.

All associations consult regularly with decision and policy makers to discuss the chances and the potential of renewable energies within the transition of the future energy system.

GEOELEC partners are leading members of these associations and used several occasions of one-to-one talks with policy to promote geothermal energy, e.g.

- Talks with representatives of German ministries, Dr. Karin Freier, Head of the Division for Solar Power, Biomass and Geothermal Power of the German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety Dr. Thomas Kölbel, EnBW, met her in Berlin to talk about a roadmap for geothermal power in Germany.

Prof. Huenges, GFZ, met her at the annual Geothermal Congress DGK to talk about the future challenges in geothermal research.

- Parliamentary evening on the potential and the chances of geothermal energy
Expert talk with Prof. Ernst Huenges, GFZ, November 2013, Berlin.

The big positive response and a lively discussion about the regulatory and economic framework for geothermal energy use in Germany showed the high interest on the issue and the need of information in this field. Parliamentarians of the German government signalized their consent for the development of the base-load energy source.

- Meeting with the municipal councillor for Berlin, Sabine Weißler, on Deep geothermal energy for cities - Risks, chances and potential

Prof. Ernst Huenges, GFZ, November 2013, Berlin.

- European Workshop on “Future Utilization of Geothermal Energy in Urban Areas” under the patronage of EU Energy Commissioner Oettinger

Participants: Prof. Ernst Huenges (GFZ), Prof. David Bruhn (GFZ),, Dr. Thomas Kölbel (EnBW), November 2012

The discussion delivered the message, that geothermal energy will play an important role in the future EU energy mix and its development should be encouraged European-wide.

Spain:

APPA has held meetings in Madrid, focused on the creation of the Spanish Geothermal Committee, with representatives of the Spanish Geothermal Technology Platform –GEOPLAT– because GEOPLAT represents all relevant stakeholders in the Spanish geothermal energy sector.

The creation of the National Geothermal Committee is expected during 2014 and will be based upon the Consultative Group of GEOPLAT. This committee will integrate the Ministries and public administrations responsible for the development of the

geothermal sector in Spain, autonomous regions and industry representatives, among others.

This committee would meet at least twice a year (one each semester). These meetings would be focused on the key issues addressed in the sector, seeking troubleshooting and establishing actions to promote their development in Spain.

The Secretariat of this committee (the GEOPLAT Secretariat, managed by APPA) will develop a preliminary structure of agents which will be provided to Steering Group members in order to complete it. Furthermore, the basic rules of procedure and the objectives of this committee, as well as the planning of the implementation and annual meetings, will be developed too. The plan is to hold the first two meetings of the Spanish Geothermal Committee one in each semester of 2014.

Estonia:

Following the EGEN letter, the Estonian Minister of Environment Mr Keit Pentus-Rosimannus answered in a letter dated 19 June 2013, and highlighted his consideration to establish a permanent Estonian geothermal committee.

Czech Republic:

Following the EGEN letter, the Czech Ministry of Industry and Trade answered in a letter dated 8 January 2014, and highlighted his welcome to the outcomes and suggestions of the activities of a newly established geothermal committee.

Lithuania :

Following the EGEN letter, the Lithuanian Ministry of Energy answered in a letter dated 18 December 2013, and highlighted his consideration for establishing a geothermal committee in Lithuania.

More Countries answered by email showing some interest about this idea: Ireland, Belgium, Poland.

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